

UOT 626/627(035.5):631.6 (075.8)

CHANNEL THAT CAN BE USED ON SLOPE, SLIDE PRONE AND SEISMIC AREAS, SWELLING AND COLLAPSING SOILS**Sabir Tehrankhan Hasanov,
Mir Movsum Anar Dadashev***"Amelioration Scientific Research Institute" LLC***Abstract**

The article provides a brief overview of irrigation systems and canals applied to slopes, landslide-prone, seismic areas, and swelling and collapsing soils. The new construction of the canal used for irrigation, energy and water supply purposes is described. In order to ensure the durability, longevity and reliability of the channel, a damping mat made of cast material is created under its cover, and the top is covered with a waterproof screen. Dowels are placed on the bottom and sides of the channel and the bottom dowel is riveted to the solid bedrock and connected with piles placed at certain distances. Drainage was placed next to the bottom dowel, an operation road was created on one side of the channel, and a berm road was created on the other side. A bathtub was built on the side of the road and a forest-bush strip was built on its bank.

Keywords: Slope; Channel; Landslide; Collapse; Swell; Soil; Structure.

Introduction. Canals used for irrigation, energy and other purposes should be built on steep slopes and mountain ridges depending on the topography of the land, the location of the irrigated area, energy and other facilities. In order to provide irrigation with its own flow and to save energy carriers, transport and distribution canals are built, as a rule, in the highest part of the area to be irrigated.

The soils through which the canal passes have different properties, including sliding, swelling and collapsing properties, and are sometimes constructed in seismic areas. Despite the fact that the channel is covered with the most ideal concrete or reinforced concrete cover during its permanent or temporary operation, leakage losses occur from their seams and from the cover itself. As a result, the soil that forms the base of the channel becomes wet, which leads to the loss of stability of the channel by creating sliding, swelling and collapsing processes. In view of the above, the need to create channels with a more advanced construction emerges.

The purpose of the study consists of increasing the stability, longevity and reliability of the channel

built on mountain slopes and seismic areas with sliding, collapsing and swelling soils.

The research object is the irrigation system and its main element, the canal.

Research methodology. Literature and research data on hydromelioration systems were collected, studied and involved in scientific analysis. Based on the acquired knowledge, the irrigation system, canal constructions which is its main element, working principles and shortcomings were determined, and a new canal built on the slope was developed.

Analysis and discussions. An irrigation system is a system of engineering devices that take irrigation water from a water source and transport it to the consumer. The irrigation system consists of different types of canals, hydrotechnical and level connected devices located on them, as well as a collector-drainage network (Fig.1). But in recent years, since the construction, working principle and destination of the collector-drainage network is different from the irrigation system, it is considered as an independent system.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the irrigation system:

1-water source; 2-water intake head device; 3-main channel; 4- inter-farm distribution channel (class channel); 5-intra-farm channel (class II channel); 6- field channel (III level channel); 7- temporary channel; 8-water collector; 9-hydronodes; 10-waterdropper or fastflowing; 11-aqueduct; 12-siphon; 13-waterthrower; 14-temporary ditches; 15-flood permeable; 16-way; 17-drainage network; 18-collector; 19-forest lane.

The main element of the irrigation system is the trunk and canals of various degrees. Hydrotechnical facilities built on these channels are considered auxiliary elements of the system.

The main canal transports irrigation water and transfers it to inter-farm (class I) canals. Inter-farm canals transport irrigation water and distribute it to intra-farm (class II) canals. Intra-farm canals transport irrigation water to inter-field distribution canals and distribute irrigation water to field and

temporary canals from there. Water from field channels is supplied to temporary channels, and from there to irrigation ditches, furrows or strips (Fig. 1).

Depending on the relief and slope of the land, channels are built in full excavation, semi-excavation - semi-pouring and full pouring (Fig. 2). In order not to damage the stability of canals built in semi-excavation-semi-casting and full casting, it is extremely important to properly manage the water level in those canals.

Fig. 2. Cross-section of channels built in drilling and casting: a – full drilling; b – semi-excavation - semi-casting; c – full casting

One of the cases that occur in practice is when highway or other canals pass through the mountain slope and are built there. Laying a channel on a slope is a very complex and responsible matter. In such conditions, the stability of the channel and the settlements, agricultural fields, communication lines, etc. located on its lower side. the safety of objects must be fully ensured. Under the mentioned conditions, the constructions of canals built mainly on a steep slope are known [1, 2, 3]. However, the known constructions of channels have some shortcomings. For example, one of the well-known canals is a slope canal built by digging and casting on a slope (Fig. 3). Although this channel is widespread, its construction is not fully justified from the point of view of technical and economic, stability and safety.

Experience shows that even if the highest quality construction materials are used, the process of seepage from the slopes and bed of the channel takes

place. That's why the danger of channel collapse increases. Such a phenomenon has been observed in practice. The danger increases, especially in collapsing and swelling soils. To ensure the stability of the channel through the foothills and steep slope, it should be built in full bore with the most favorable hydraulic radius. The bed and slopes of the channel should be lined with high-quality reinforced concrete lining, and a waterproof curtain should be placed under the lining. In order to prevent the flood waters generated on the slopes from entering the channel during heavy rainfall, a tub should be built on the berm of the channel, on the side of the slope, and connected to the storm drain in the appropriate part of the channel, mainly at the end of the slope. In order to increase the resistance of the channel against landslides and earthquakes, it should be provided with additional elements.

Fig. 3. Cross-section of the channel built on the slope [2]:
1-canal casting dam; 2-channel; 3-berm; 4-slope; 5-concrete lining against filtration.

The disadvantage of known canals is that the water seeping from the bottom and slopes of the canal can lead to a decrease in the stability of the canal, rapid collapse and flooding of settlements and facilities located under the canal. At the same time, it is generally not allowed to build a canal with this type of construction if the area the canal passes through, i.e., the slope, is prone to sliding.

Canals with a trapezoidal cross-section are also known [4, pp. 208-210], which are built in full excavation on the mountain slope, which is prone to sliding and consists of collapsing soils.

Since the known channel is built on a landslide-prone patch, the stability of both the channel and the landslide-prone soil mass located on its upper side is provided by the soil mass located in the lower part. However, the water seeping through the canal causes complete wetting of the soil mass intended as a support, and this leads to a decrease in the adhesion force within that soil mass, loss of stability, and ultimately, the slope slides and the canal collapses. On the other hand, the stability of the landslide-prone soil mass located above the channel was not ensured by any additional device, for example, a retaining wall or the constructive solution of the channel itself. Therefore, there is always a danger of soil mass sliding on the slope, especially during heavy rains, this danger increases even more. At the same time, in the event of heavy rainfall, the floodwaters flowing down the slope and the materials brought by it directly enter the channel unhindered, causing it to be filled with silt and foreign objects and cause its premature failure. The known channel does not have

the ability to work in swelling and collapsing soils. Thus, when moisture in the channel bed increases and decreases, the channel swells and collapses, which leads to washing and disintegration of the bed. As you can see, the known channels built on the mountain slope prone to landslides and in seismic areas are structurally incomplete and their stability is not ensured.

Taking into account the above, a new construction of the channel built in seismic areas, on mountain slopes with sliding, collapsing and swelling soils was developed. [5].

In order to eliminate the process of swelling and subsidence, a damping mat was created on the bed and slopes of the canal, and a screen made of waterproof material was placed on top of the damping mat to prevent water seeping from the canal. To prevent sliding, dowels were placed on the bottom and sides of the channel and the bottom dowel was connected to a stable bedrock with riveted piles at specified distances. In order to catch the flood waters flowing down the slope and prevent them from entering the main channel, a berm - a tub was built on the slope side of the road, and a forest-bush strip was built on its upper - slope side to extinguish the kinetic energy of the water flowing down the slope and to prevent foreign objects from entering the tub. During the winter period, a drain was built next to the bottom pile in order to prevent the collapse of the reinforced concrete lining due to the subsidence or heaving of the soil in the moistened canal bed during the rains and to remove the ground water collected by filtering into the canal bed (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Cross-section of the channel built on the slope: 1 – the course of the channel; 2 – reinforced concrete cladding; 3 – dowel; 4 – damping mattress from casting material; 5 – waterproof screen; 6 – bed rock; 7 – pile; 8 – drainage; 9 – slope; 10 – exploitation way; 11 – berm road; 12 – bathtub; 13 – forest-shrub strip.

The irrigation channel consists of a trapezoidal cross-sectional prismatic channel 1, the sides and bottom of the channel lining 2 are equipped with splines 3, a damping mat 4 is made of cast material under the lining, and a waterproof screen 5 is placed on top of it. The bottom pile 3 is connected to the bedrock 6 with riveted piles 7, and drainage 8 is placed next to it. On the left bank of the canal, on the lower side of the mountain slope 9, an operational road 10 was created, and on the right bank of the canal, a berm-road 11 was created, a tub 12 was built to catch and divert flood waters, and a forest-shrub strip 13 was built on its bank.

The channel works as follows:

The required amount of water is released from the water source 1 into the canal channel, and the water moves along the channel's reinforced concrete cover 2 and is delivered to the required place. When water is transported in the channel, the water seeping through the reinforced concrete cover 2 is prevented by the waterproof screen 5 laid on the damping mat 4 and eliminates the moisture of the soil forming the bed of the channel. The landslide-prone mass of the slope through which the canal passes becomes wet during rainfall, and the slope 9 is in danger of landslides. At this time, shallow splines 3 placed on the sides and bottom of the channel, as well as piles 7 riveted to the bedrock 6, prevent sliding. Leaking water collected under the channel (bed) due to rainfall is filtered through the damping cast materials laid on its bottom and slopes, enters the drainage 8 and is removed from there. During a heavy downpour, the water flowing down the slope 9 enters the forest-shrub strip 13, and from there it enters the basin 12, while foreign objects brought by the flood (silt, stone chips and fragments, tree branches and stumps, debris, etc.) and the kinetic energy of the flood is extinguished, the flood waters are discharged without entering the tub and flowing into the main channel. In this way, the danger of silting and filling of the channel with foreign objects is eliminated. Operation road 10 and berm road 11 are used to operate the channel and the facilities located on it (sluice, regulating gates, etc.). Berm-way 11 also increases channel stability.

The damping mat 4 and the bottom pile 3 absorb swelling and subsidence deformations when the soil forming the canal channel collapses or swells, and as a result prevents damage to the reinforced concrete 2 lining of the canal, as well as the canal as a whole and the hydrotechnical facilities on it.

Compared to known channels, the proposed channel has a more perfect construction and characteristics, unlike its predecessors, it can be used in the most complex geological and hydrogeological conditions - hard slopes prone to landslides, seismic areas, swelling and collapsing soils.

Compared with known canals, the protection of settlements and other objects located at the bottom of the proposed canal is fully ensured, it has no danger of flying and collapsing, since this canal has no seepage losses, its useful work coefficient ranges from 0.99 to 1.00, silt and other foreign objects due to the fact that there is no danger of siltation, the operating costs are reduced to a minimum.

Conclusion: Channels built in seismic areas, slopes prone to landslides, seismic areas, swelling and collapsing soils should be prepared in special structures. Otherwise, as a result of seepage from the channel, soil subsidence and swelling, the channel may collapse and the slope may slide.

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